

FAIR strategy implementation
10 October 2022
BRAINSTORMING

Where do we want to be in 3 years?

FAIR RDM education for students (bachelor, master, PhD)

Shared understanding of central concepts (RDM core elements, OS practices, FAIR data stewardship, ...)

Domain-specific understanding of central concepts

Infrastructure in place and working

Infrastructure governance in place and working

Internal organizational structure/governance in place

Data are recognized as a valuable research output in itself - giving merits to creators

Funding for data management

Easy and efficient support for infrastructures and system resources

Data governance guideline and support

Training for data stewardship (both leadership and researchers)

FAIRification Agile Framework

It's hard not to do the "right thing" reg. DM

Efteruddannelse in DM (FAIR, GDPR, etc) available on all universities for all fagområder

We all agree on the difference on FAIR, Open Science, Open Acces etc

Clear understanding for data responsibility and rights "in the long run". Common policies

National Data Management Code of Conduct

(FAIR) DM is an integrated part of BA/MS/PhD (del af studieordningen)

We all agree on what a Data Steward is

Changed incentive structure for hiring & promotions that include FAIR RDM as research quality factor

Within-university alignment on level of FAIR to obtain (as a starting point) followed by between-university alignment

DMPs are a fully integrated part of the research process

Awareness of FAIR throughout the organisation

Strong focus on RDM education. First step students/young researchers, second the older generations. Educational resources in place and offered by default.

Researchers' understanding that FAIR benefits them directly (focus on incentives)

Multiple data stewards employed across the university

Clear understanding of division of responsibilities for FAIR

Alignment between existing procedures (eg for RDM, IS, GDPR, grant application) and a system to collect all info into one place

At least one data lead / coordinator (non-PI) at each department

Data steward education program (MS level) - industry and academic

Data management career track set up

Multi-level leadership on data strategy and tangible goals

Convert DMPs into a more natural / useful form

Driving strategy with available user / usage data

Establish rewards for good open science practices (for researchers)

Make the data manager <-> researcher relationship bi-directional

Common DM measures for institutions to gauge their progress and successes

I think there are many more questions than asking, "where do we want to be in 3 years, and where are we now?"

The FAIR Implementation Strategy will require Data Stewards and an educated workforce to assist with implementing any RDM strategy.

Where will we find talent? Should the Libraries or should the University provide Data Stewards? Who will teach the skills needed to educate Data Stewards?

There has to be a comprehensive approach to solving this problem. It should come from the national level because it will take money.

Will Libraries retrain current librarians to become Data Stewards?

Will the country reorganize and invest in a library school and add a curriculum focusing on Data Stewardship? It's the biggest challenge we are facing as we continue to create data and neglect the need to educate a workforce on how to handle data.

Here are some of the challenges we face :

- 1. Infrastructure (Tools and Services)*
- 2. Quality of data management plans*
- 3. Challenges in researcher RDM practices*
- 4. Alignment of research management and data management*
- 5. Resourcing*
- 6. Researcher openness*
- 7. Research data governance*

In all disciplines, research funders expect grant applicants and grant holders to explain how they will manage their data and to comply with their Data Management Plans. Awareness of these policies and services is key to writing successful funding applications. The earlier researchers receive assistance, the lesser the eventual risks for their projects.

Training and support opportunities for research staff and students should not overlook the aspects around personal/sensitive data and databases, as a large proportion of researchers use these as part of their projects. Using personal computers and commercial cloud services to store research data represents a clear security risk for any data and a potential breach of security regulations if these are personal/sensitive data. An increasing number of funders expect research data to be preserved for at least ten years. Whether using an institutional facility or a discipline-specific repository, researchers should ensure they know how to find reliable archiving facilities.

The lack of clarity on where to find solutions to all of the challenges cited by research staff is a worrying observation. Academic faculties should be strongly encouraged to consider appointing/designating permanent staff members to assist researchers with data management in their subject disciplines. Following these recommendations will help to avoid rushed and potentially costly short-term decisions; a lack of support when problems arise; and the outdating of skills and standards.

Education / Training

How do we get there?

3 years from now

Where are we now?

- broken training material
- Fragmentation
- General education on overarching principles, need for discipline-specific RDM education
- Fragmentation of concepts and practices (down to individual research groups or labs)
- Lack of infrastructure, e.g. for storing and sharing data, leading to fragmentation of practices
- Disconnect between experiments, analysis, and publication (reproducibility/ replicability)

3 years from now

- Shared understanding of central concepts (RDM core elements, OS practices, FAIR data stewardship, ...)
- Domain-specific understanding of central concepts (RDM core elements, OS practices, FAIR data stewardship, ...)
- Strong focus on RDM education. First step students/young researchers, second the older generations. Educational resources in place and offered by default.
- (FAIR) DM is an integrated part of BA/MS/PhD (del af studieordningen)
- Changed incentive structure for hiring & promotions that include FAIR RDM as research quality factor
- we all agree on the difference on FAIR, Open Science, Open Acces etc
- Data management career track set up
- FAIR RDM education for students (bachelor, master, PhD)
- Awareness of what FAIR throughout the organisation
- Data steward education program (MS level) - industry and academic
- Training for data stewardship (both leadership and researchers)

Researchers	Research institution management	Funders	Ministry/Agency Higher education and science	Other
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get acquainted with basic concepts and good RDM practices Take active part in the data management training of students and junior researchers under their supervision, e.g. by reviewing & discussing DMPs. RDM training must be acknowledged as a supervisor responsibility. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finance disciplinary RDM support at the institutions Implement mandatory RDM training and DMPs at the start of BA/MA and PhD programs Finance an institutional RDM support organization Prioritize RDM skills training for students and early-career researchers Determine the minimum responsibilities that supervisors have in the data management training of students and junior researchers and make sure all supervisors know about this (e.g. capture in supervision contracts?) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requirements regarding FAIR RDM in funded projects Provide funds to finance FAIR RDM In funding programmes to fund entire research groups and or educational programmes (e.g. where a bunch of PhD students can be hired) make it mandatory to include a description of / plan for how OS/RDM training and education will be carried out (e.g. could be a question in the DMPs) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resources for FAIR RDM education National digitalization strategy that comprises education institutions (schools), academia and industry Merit FAIR science "just done right" instead of "fast science" 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Journals: Requirements to publish data and code together with the articles

Governance / Organisation / Policies / Definitions

How do we get there?

3 years from now

Where are we now?

- National understanding of research integrity (code of conduct)
- Stakeholder requirements for FAIR data management (funders, publishers, ETC)
- No governance at universities at present...just loose initiatives.
- Subject specific FAIR data management governed by PIs?
- At KU: new policy that poses minimum requirements for FAIR
- Some data driven organisations like DST have a clear governance and procedures
- Not enough FTEs working on RDM

- Internal organizational structure/ governance in place
- DMP are a fully integrated part of the research process
- FAIRification Agile Framework
- Driving strategy with available user / usage data
- Funding for data management
- Alignment between existing procedures (eg for RDM, IS, GDPR, grant application) - a system to collect all info into one place
- Changed incentive structure for hiring & promotions that include FAIR RDM as research quality factor
- Clear understanding of division of responsibilities for FAIR
- Common DM measures for institutions to gauge their progress and successes
- National Data Management Code of Conduct
- Within-university alignment on level of FAIR, to obtain (as a starting point) followed by between-university
- Clear understanding for data responsibility and rights "in the long run". Common policies
- Multi-level leadership on data strategy and tangible goals

<p>Researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote using standards in their discipline Within research groups make standardized plans for RDM (eg preservation plans, metadata overview of data sets) and appoint a role/person to maintain and update the plans / metadata. 	<p>Research institution management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Listen to researchers' needs to ensure FAIR RDM Prioritize data management initiatives, e.g. establish data stewards Include OS/FAIR/RDM in overarching university strategy (so that we have a 'coat hanger' to hang future RDM projects up on - simply because anything with a clear link to university strategy is prioritised) Programmes to implement national strategies and local policies. use the existing research committee systems to create a governance structure We need an organisation (high level standing committee / forum) that makes a plan for implementation with prioritisation of initiatives Adopt mandatory courses for students and junior researchers in data management (e.g. as fixed component of PhD programmes) Establish umbrella organisation og RDM support staff for information sharing up and down the 'university levels' (central-faculty-institute-research group) Institutional policies based on CoC and strategy 	<p>Funders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DK funders should follow HorizonEurope regarding demands for DMPs and FAIR Requirements for Open Data. 	<p>Ministry/Agency Higher education and science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish a working group that drafts a code of conduct for data management & updates the existing CoC Make money available for FAIRification, e.g. where universities can employ data stewards 	<p>Other</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A National Data Steward(ship) Network
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